

Online Teaching-Learning in Medical Education: A Multicentric Cross-Sectional Study on Perception and Challenges of Teachers and Students during COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:

Background: During the COVID-19 lockdown, the entire educational system, from elementary to tertiary levels, collapsed. This led to a significant shift towards e-learning, with teaching conducted remotely on digital platforms. Students are likely to face various educational challenges in the future.

Aim and Objectives: To assess the perceptions and challenges of teachers and students in online medical education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology: A multicentric cross-sectional study was conducted among teachers and UG students from four medical colleges (Government & Private) in Gujarat. Self-administered online questionnaires were distributed through google form and perceptions-challenges of online T-L were collected using a 5-point Likert scale.

Results: Out of 367 responses, 102 were from teachers and 265 from students. Teachers viewed online T-L as a good pandemic alternative, helping complete the syllabus and enhance faculty technical skills. Students, however, had a neutral perception. Major challenges included limited interaction, poor internet connectivity, data limits, and distractions.

Conclusion: In conclusion, participants had mixed views on online teaching and learning (T-L). While most support integrating both online and offline methods in the future, careful planning is needed to address challenges and maintain quality.

Keywords: Online teaching-learning, Covid-19 pandemic, Perception, Challenges.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused an unprecedented disruption in education, affecting nearly 1.6 billion learners across over 190 countries.[1] In India, the closure of educational institutions halted face-to-face learning to curb the virus's spread. Policymakers faced the challenge of mitigating academic losses during the lockdown.[2] To maintain the academic calendar, the Indian government, UGC, and medical universities mandated online classes.[3]

However, this shift brought challenges like reduced student engagement, limited technical skills, unreliable internet, overburdened faculty, and waning motivation among educators.[4] While many have embraced online teaching, some faculty members have struggled, focusing on identifying the system's shortcomings.[5] Online teaching and learning can be understood in various ways. Singh and Thurman

(2019) define it as educational experiences conducted either synchronously or asynchronously through devices like mobile phones and laptops with internet access.[6] Howlett et al. defined electronic or online learning as the utilization of electronic technology and media to provide, assist, and improve both learning and teaching, involving interaction between learners and teachers using online resources.[7]

The effectiveness of e-learning hinges on several factors, such as accessibility, the adoption of suitable methods, course content, and assessment criteria. E-learning, much like any other teaching method, has its pros and cons for both students and teachers. In addition to the health advantages of e-learning amid the COVID-19 outbreak, it also offers increased convenience, access to resources at any time and from anywhere, and helps in cutting

costs. Additionally, it contributes to environmental benefits, such as reduced carbon emissions from decreased traffic.[8,9,10]

In the past, e-learning, distance education, and correspondence courses were often viewed as components of non-formal education. However, the current trends suggest that these modes of learning may gradually supplant the traditional formal education system, especially if the current circumstances persist. Amid the pandemic crisis, educational institutions worldwide are increasingly turning to e-learning to adapt to the new normal, providing students with alternative means to continue their education. Educators are also exploring a variety of e-teaching platforms to ensure that students have the best possible learning experience under these challenging conditions.[11] The unprecedented threat posed by the coronavirus has made it clear that the future of education may be fraught with significant challenges. Students may face obstacles in accessing quality education, gaining hands-on experience, participating in laboratory work, engaging in peer tutoring, and receiving remedial instruction.[12]

This study holds significant future importance. As the pandemic has accelerated the adoption of digital education, understanding these experiences will be crucial for shaping the future of medical education. Insights gained from this research can guide the development of more effective online teaching strategies, address the unique challenges of medical training in a virtual environment, and ensure that future medical professionals receive the high-quality education necessary for their roles. This study will also contribute to the broader discourse on how medical education can evolve to remain resilient and adaptable in the face of future global challenges.

Amid the global health crisis, both online educators and students hold distinct perspectives and concerns regarding the advantages and disadvantages of this mode of instruction. This study, therefore, aimed to explore perceptions and challenges encountered by teachers and students in online teaching and learning within medical education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Material & Methods:

This study was designed as a multicentric cross-sectional investigation, with prior ethical approval (No. CUSMC/IEC(HR)/RP/4/2022/Final Approval/87/2022) obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC) of C. U. Shah Medical College.

The research was conducted across four medical colleges in Gujarat—two government and two private - randomly selected from a pool of six government and twelve private institutions. The

study targeted two distinct populations: students and teachers. All the teachers and students from the four selected medical colleges were included in the study, with no individuals being excluded based on specific criteria. Participation was voluntary for both teachers and students, and informed consent was obtained through a statement included in the survey form. Initially, a sample size of 330 participants was determined (25 teachers and 50 students from each college, with an additional 10% to account for non-responses). However, the final sample included 367 respondents (102 teachers and 265 undergraduate students), and all responses were considered for analysis. The study lasted for one year, from June 2021 to May 2022.

A pre-tested, semi-structured, validated questionnaire was employed for data collection, with validation achieved through peer review, expert evaluation, and piloting. The questionnaire, created using Google Forms, was distributed via WhatsApp groups to teachers and students from the selected medical colleges, who were instructed to respond to each question based on their knowledge and experience. The questionnaire was organized into several sections, including socio-demographic information, teaching experience, satisfaction levels, and perceptions and challenges related to online teaching and learning. Participants' views on online classes were measured using a Five-Point Likert Scale, where 5 represented strong agreement and 1 represented strong disagreement. Satisfaction levels were similarly rated, with 5 indicating high satisfaction and 1 indicating high dissatisfaction. Additionally, the questionnaire asked about preferences for devices, modes of communication, and the frequency and duration of online classes for both teachers and students.

To simplify data analysis, responses on the Five-Point Likert Scale were categorized into two groups: grades 1 and 2 as dissatisfied or disagreed (Disfavour online T-L or disagree with the challenges mentioned), and grades 4 and 5 as satisfied or agreed (Favour online T-L or agree with the challenges mentioned). Responses with a neutral grade of 3 were excluded from statistical analysis. Data collected via Google Forms was automatically compiled into MS Excel, and SPSS version 20 was used for analysis. We analyzed the data using frequency distribution, percentage, mean, mode, and standard deviation to conduct descriptive statistics. Fisher's exact test was employed to assess whether the response distributions for each item significantly deviated from the null hypothesis. Content validity was evaluated using the Content Validity Index (CVI), with questionnaires validated by six subject experts; an I-CVI value of 0.83 or higher was deemed acceptable. Reliability and internal consistency were measured through Cronbach's

Alpha, with values ranging from 0.7 to 1 indicating acceptable to excellent consistency. Statistical significance was determined by p-values of less than 0.05 and 0.01.

Results:

A total of 367 responses were gathered, comprising 102 teachers and 265 students.

Table 1 provides an overview of the participants' demographic profiles. The mean age \pm SD was

40.44 ± 8.46 years for teachers and 20.37 ± 4.48 years for students, with a male-to-female ratio of 6:4 in both groups. Most of the teachers held positions at or above the assistant professor level, while the majority of student respondents (66.42%) were in the third MBBS Part-I phase.

Table 1 also shows the distribution of teachers and students by institution. Notably, more than two-thirds of the teachers (68%) had over seven years of teaching experience.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the participants

Demographic Variables	Teachers (N = 102)		Students (N = 265)	
	Variable	Freq (%)	Variable	Freq (%)
Age	≤ 30	10 (9.8)	18 – 20	146 (55.1)
	31 – 40	48 (47.1)	21 – 25	117 (44.2)
	41 – 50	29 (28.4)	26 – 30	02 (0.7)
	≥ 51	15 (14.7)		
Gender	Male	65 (63.7)	Male	159 (60)
	Female	37 (36.3)	Female	106 (40)
Designation	Professor	26 (25.5)	First MBBS	39 (14.7)
	Associate Prof	30 (29.4)	Second MBBS	43 (16.2)
	Assistant Prof	33 (32.4)	Third MBBS-I	176 (66.4)
	Tutor/SR	13 (12.7)	Third MBBS-II	7 (2.7)
College	Government	61 (59.8)	Government	124 (46.8)
	Private	41 (40.2)	Private	141 (53.2)
Teaching Experience	0-3	16 (15.7)		
	4-6	16 (15.7)		
	7-10	24 (23.5)		
	> 10	46 (45.1)		

The summary of study participants' experience with online T-L is presented in table 2. The study evaluated participants' technological expertise, given the necessity of computer and internet skills for online classes. Results showed that most teachers (68.6%) and students (66.4%) had a strong grasp of educational technology. Nearly 90% of teachers had prior online teaching experience before the COVID-19 pandemic, compared to 36% of students. Of the 91 experienced teachers, 62% had 1-3 years of experience, while 33% had less than a year. Online classes were initiated at all selected medical colleges in response to the suspension of traditional sessions due to the pandemic. Regarding class frequency, 37% of teachers held online sessions once a week, 18.7% once every 15 days, and 15.4% once a month.

Students attended online sessions more frequently, with half participating more than four times per week. The average class duration for both groups ranged from 30 to 60 minutes. Student responses to online classes varied, reflecting diverse attitudes and experiences.

Figure 1 illustrates the overall satisfaction levels of teachers and students with online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic. As shown, a significant portion of the study participants expressed satisfaction, with 62% of teachers and 38.9% of students reporting positive experiences with the online sessions. The difference in satisfaction levels between the two groups was also found to be statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.01 for teachers and 0.0041 for students.

Table 2: Participants' experience with online teaching and learning

Experience	Teachers		Students	
	Variable	Freq (%)	Variable	Freq (%)
How familiar are you with the use of technology in education?	Good	70 (68.6)	Good	176 (66.4)
	Average	28 (27.5)	Average	85 (32.1)
	Poor	4 (3.9)	Poor	4 (1.5)
Have you conducted/attended online class before Covid 19 pandemic?	Yes	91 (89.2)	Yes	96 (36.2)
	No	11 (10.8)	No	169 (63.8)
Teaching Experience of online T-L	< 1 Year	30 (33)		
	1-3 Year	57 (62.6)		
	> 3 Year	4 (4.4)		
Frequency of Online class	Once in month	14 (15.4)	Once in month	7 (2.6)
	Once in fortnight	17 (18.7)	Once in fortnight	5 (1.9)
	Once in week	34 (37.3)	Once in week	26 (9.8)
	2 times in a week	15 (16.5)	2 times in a week	45 (17)
	4 times in a week	5 (5.5)	4 times in a week	49 (18.5)
	> 4 times in a week	6 (6.6)	> 4 times in a week	133 (50.2)
Average duration of online class	< 30 minutes	4 (4.4)	< 30 minutes	4 (1.5)
	30-45 minutes	55 (60.4)	30-45 minutes	102 (38.5)
	45-60 minutes	32 (35.2)	45-60 minutes	133 (50.2)
	> 60 minutes	0 (0)	> 60 minutes	26 (9.8)
Response of students	Excellent	7 (7.7)		
	Good	39 (42.8)		
	Fair	37 (40.7)		
	Poor	8 (8.8)		

Figure 1: Level of satisfaction (%) towards online T-L of participants

With numerous online class tools available in the market, participants were asked to identify the ones they used for their online classes, with the option to select multiple tools. Zoom emerged as the most popular platform among both teachers and students. Other frequently used tools included Google Meet, WhatsApp, YouTube, and Google Classroom, following closely behind Zoom. Table 3 highlights participants' preferences for online classes. Among the 102 teachers, nearly 90% favoured using either a laptop or both a laptop and smartphone for online sessions. In contrast, a majority of students (56%)

preferred attending online classes via smartphone. WhatsApp emerged as the preferred mode of communication for online teaching and learning in both groups, with 79.4% of teachers and 84.2% of students favoring it. More than three-quarters (76.5%) of teachers preferred holding one or two online classes per week, with 68.6% favoring a class duration of 30-45 minutes. On the other hand, most students preferred three or more online classes per week, with a duration of 30-60 minutes per session. Interestingly, 65% of students

expressed a desire to participate in online assessments.

Table 3: Teachers' and students' preference for online classes

Preference	Teachers		Students	
	Variable	Freq (%)	Variable	Freq (%)
Preferred Device for Online T-L	Smart Phone	5 (4.9)	Smart Phone	149 (56.2)
	Tablet	1 (1.0)	Tablet	33 (12.5)
	Laptop	48 (47.1)	Laptop	33 (12.5)
	Desktop	6 (5.9)	Desktop	2 (0.8)
	Both Smart Phone & Laptop	42 (41.2)	Both Smart Phone & Laptop	48 (18.1)
	Others	0 (0.0)	Others	0 (0.0)
Preferred mode of Communication for Online T-L	Text Message	5 (4.9)	Text Message	11 (4.2)
	Whatsapp	81 (79.4)	Whatsapp	223 (84.2)
	E-mail	4 (3.9)	E-mail	5 (1.9)
	Google Classroom	9 (8.8)	Google Classroom	25 (9.4)
	Moodle	1 (1.0)	Moodle	1 (0.4)
	College Website	2 (2.0)	College Website	0 (0.0)
Preferred frequency of Online class per week	One	41 (40.2)	One	19 (7.2)
	Two	37 (36.3)	Two	28 (10.6)
	Three	15 (14.7)	Three	57 (21.5)
	Four	6 (5.9)	Four	64 (24.2)
	Five	2 (2.0)	Five	37 (14.0)
	> Five	1 (1.0)	> Five	60 (22.6)
Preferred duration of Online class	< 30 Minutes	6 (5.9)	< 30 Minutes	15 (5.7)
	30-45 Minutes	70 (68.6)	30-45 Minutes	136 (51.3)
	45-60 Minutes	26 (25.5)	45-60 Minutes	101 (38.1)
	> 60 Minutes	0 (0.0)	> 60 Minutes	13 (4.9)
Do you like to attend online ex-am/assessment?			Yes	174 (65.7)
			No	91 (34.3)

Overview of teachers' perceptions of online classes is offered in table 4.

About 80% view online teaching as a valuable alternative during the COVID-19 pandemic, enhancing technical knowledge and aiding syllabus completion, with this view being statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). However, only 40% believe online classes effectively clear student doubts or reduce the communication gap, without statistical significance ($P > 0.05$). Just 34% find online teaching more comfortable than traditional methods ($P = 0.224$), and 35% feel it increases their workload ($P = 0.817$).

Over half reported challenges in engaging students and found online teaching more time-consuming, both statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Most

teachers also noted significant distractions and a lack of face-to-face interaction ($P < 0.0001$).

The perceptions of students regarding online teaching and learning are documented in Table 5. A significant portion of students found online teaching beneficial for effective learning (45%) and appreciated its accessibility (58%), with these results showing a statistically significant difference. However, many students expressed dissatisfaction, with 35% disagreeing that online education is more engaging, 40% finding it less interesting or enjoyable, and 42% noting ineffective communication during online sessions.

The high internal consistency of these perceptions is supported by an alpha coefficient value of 0.836, indicating that the survey items were reliably aligned in capturing students' experiences.

Table 4: Perception of teachers towards online T-L (5 Point Likert Scale with 5 strongly agree and 1 – strongly disagree)

Perception towards online T-L Likert Scale	Disagreed Group Freq (%)		Neutral Freq (%)	Agreed Group Freq (%)		P Value	Mean Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
A good alternative during Covid 19 pandemic	1 (1.0)	1 (1.0)	16 (15.7)	23 (22.5)	61 (59.8)	< 0.0001	4.39
Helpful in increasing technical knowledge of teachers	0 (0.0)	5 (4.9)	16 (15.7)	25 (24.5)	56 (54.9)	< 0.0001	4.29
Helpful in completing the syllabus	2 (2.0)	3 (2.9)	14 (13.7)	31 (30.4)	52 (51.0)	< 0.0001	4.25
Helpful in clearing student's doubts	6 (5.9)	24 (23.5)	30 (29.4)	25 (24.5)	17 (16.7)	0.194	3.23
Reduces communication gap between teachers and students	10 (9.8)	20 (19.6)	32 (31.4)	24 (23.5)	16 (15.7)	0.281	3.16
More comfortable than offline teaching	24 (23.5)	23 (22.5)	20 (19.6)	21 (20.6)	14 (13.7)	0.224	2.78
Students get more engaged in online teaching	27 (26.5)	26 (25.5)	20 (19.6)	18 (17.6)	11 (10.8)	< 0.05	2.61
It increases the burden of work on teachers	19 (18.6)	20 (19.6)	27 (26.5)	23 (22.5)	13 (12.7)	0.817	2.91
Time consuming than classroom teaching	22 (21.6)	28 (27.5)	21 (20.6)	21 (20.6)	10 (9.8)	< 0.05	2.70
More expensive than classroom teaching	32 (31.4)	20 (19.6)	33 (32.4)	14 (13.7)	3 (2.9)	< 0.0001	2.37
Lots of distraction while taking online session	5 (4.9)	7 (6.9)	16 (15.7)	48 (47.1)	26 (25.5)	< 0.0001	3.81
It lacks face-to-face interaction	0 (0.0)	4 (3.9)	5 (4.9)	38 (37.3)	55 (53.9)	< 0.0001	4.41
Overall Mean Score							3.41

* Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.493, CVI = 0.92

Table 5: Perception of students towards online T-L (5 Point Likert Scale with 5 strongly agree and 1 – strongly disagree)

Perception towards online T-L Likert Scale	Disagreed Group Freq (%)		Neutral Freq (%)	Agreed Group Freq (%)		P Value	Mean Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
How effectively did the online teaching help you learn?	12 (4.5)	39 (14.7)	95 (35.8)	69 (26.0)	50 (18.9)	< 0.0001	3.40
How easy was the access to online teaching?	8 (3.0)	35 (13.2)	68 (25.7)	89 (33.6)	65 (24.5)	< 0.0001	3.63
How engaging you found online teaching?	35 (13.2)	58 (21.9)	102 (38.5)	45 (17.0)	25 (9.4)	= 0.08	2.88
How interesting/enjoyable you found online teaching?	35 (13.2)	70 (26.4)	80 (30.2)	40 (15.1)	40 (15.1)	= 0.07	2.92
Level of effectiveness of communication in online teaching	48 (18.1)	63 (23.8)	83 (31.3)	38 (12.5)	33 (12.5)	< 0.01	2.79
Overall Mean Score							3.12

* Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.836, CVI = 1.0

Table 6 highlights the key challenges teachers faced while conducting online classes.

The most pressing issue was the limited or non-existent face-to-face interaction with students,

coupled with a noticeable lack of student engagement. These challenges were statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Additionally, teachers struggled with poor internet connectivity (51%),

insufficient technical knowledge (50%), and limitations in data speed or availability (38%). The reliability of these findings is underscored by a

Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.726, indicating acceptable internal consistency across the survey items.

Table 6: Challenges faced by teachers in delivering online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic (5 Point Likert Scale with 5 – strongly agree and 1 – strongly disagree)

Challenges	Disagreed Group Freq (%)		Neutral Freq (%)	Agreed Group Freq (%)		P Value	Mean Score
	1	2		3	4		
Poor internet connectivity	8 (7.8)	17 (16.7)	25 (24.5)	26 (25.5)	26 (25.5)	< 0.01	3.44
Data limit/Data speed	9 (8.8)	20 (19.6)	34 (33.3)	19 (18.6)	20 (19.6)	= 0.274	3.21
Lack of technical knowledge	17 (16.7)	13 (12.7)	21 (20.6)	31 (30.4)	20 (19.6)	< 0.05	3.24
Lack of student interest	0 (0.0)	5 (4.9)	13 (12.7)	46 (45.1)	38 (37.3)	< 0.0001	4.15
Little/no face-to-face interaction	2 (2.0)	2 (2.0)	8 (7.8)	34 (33.3)	56 (54.9)	< 0.0001	4.37
Time consuming	18 (17.6)	20 (19.6)	30 (29.4)	21 (20.6)	13 (12.7)	= 0.723	2.91
Overall Mean Score							3.55

* Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.726, CVI = 1.0

In Table 7, the difficulties that students encountered while participating in online sessions during the COVID-19 pandemic are detailed.

Nearly half of the students reported significant difficulties, including poor internet connectivity, data limitations, slow data speeds, and the lack of face-to-face interaction. Other prominent challenges included perceived poor faculty engagement and an inadequate learning

environment. These challenges were statistically significant across most categories, reinforcing the widespread impact on students' online learning experiences.

The Cronbach's coefficient alpha value of 0.796 further indicates a strong internal consistency among the survey items, validating the reliability of these findings.

Table 7: Challenges faced by students while attending online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic (5 Point Likert Scale with 5 – strongly agree and 1 – strongly disagree)

Challenges	Disagreed Group Freq (%)		Neutral Freq (%)	Agreed Group Freq (%)		P Value	Mean Score
	1	2		3	4		
Poor internet connectivity	27 (10.2)	42 (15.8)	68 (25.7)	63 (23.8)	65 (24.5)	< 0.0001	3.37
Data limit/Data speed	22 (8.3)	47 (17.7)	62 (23.4)	55 (20.8)	79 (29.8)	< 0.0001	3.46
Lack of technical knowledge	54 (20.4)	51 (19.2)	90 (34.0)	39 (14.7)	31 (11.7)	< 0.01	2.78
Lack of faculty interest	41 (15.5)	55 (20.8)	84 (31.7)	47 (17.7)	38 (14.3)	= 0.457	2.95
Little/no face-to-face interaction	20 (7.5)	39 (14.7)	72 (27.2)	59 (22.3)	75 (28.3)	< 0.0001	3.49
Timing is not suitable	53 (20.0)	55 (20.8)	87 (32.8)	35 (13.2)	35 (13.2)	< 0.01	2.79
Unavailability of device	89 (33.6)	57 (21.5)	64 (24.2)	29 (10.9)	26 (9.8)	< 0.0001	2.42
Poor learning environment	52 (19.6)	54 (20.4)	70 (26.4)	46 (17.4)	43 (16.2)	= 0.251	2.90
Overall Mean Score							3.02

* Cronbach's Alpha value = 0.796, CVI = 0.88

After the Covid-19 pandemic, the majority of teachers (57%) expressed a preference for a combination of online and classroom teaching when asked about their preferred mode of instruction. Conversely, most students (50%) indicated a desire for classroom teaching in the future.

Discussion:

The Covid-19 pandemic profoundly disrupted global education, shifting traditional classroom teaching to online formats. This unprecedented change caused significant stress for both teachers and students, who were unprepared for the sudden transition. Our study aimed to assess the perceptions and challenges faced by medical educators and learners during this period to inform future academic strategies and address ongoing disruptions. Our research revealed that 68.6% of teachers and 66.4% of students had strong technological proficiency, a significant improvement over previous studies where such figures ranged from 13% to 56%. [5,13,14] Prior online teaching experience was held by 89.2% of teachers and 36.2% of students, compared to 47.2% reported by Muthuprasad T et al. [15] Satisfaction with online education was noted by about two-thirds of teachers and one-third of students, aligning with global trends of increased satisfaction during the pandemic. [16-21] The study identified Zoom, Google Meet, Google Classroom, WhatsApp, and YouTube as the predominant e-learning tools, echoing findings from other research. [5,20-25] In this study teachers viewed online learning positively, recognizing its benefits for technical skill enhancement, good alternative of classroom learning, solving student's queries and reduce communication gap and syllabus completion. Students appreciated the accessibility and effectiveness of online learning compared to traditional classroom method but also noted challenges such as reduced face-to-face interaction, less interesting and communication difficulties. These findings are consistent with broader research, including studies by Faiz Tuma. [26] In 36 medical schools in Korea, a study conducted by Kyong Jee Kim et al also discovered that online education is an effective resource for student learning, providing sufficient quality content and leading to satisfaction. [27] A number of studies carried out in different countries also emphasized almost identical perspectives of both the faculty and students regarding online education. [25,28-31] It is crucial for medical faculty to transition from being mere providers of information to becoming facilitators of learning, and e-learning tools can assist in achieving this objective by enabling the sharing of a wide range of online resources. [32]

Initial resistance to e-learning due to inadequate training and technical issues gradually diminished

as participants adapted. However, persistent challenges included poor internet connectivity, lack of engagement, and suboptimal learning environments. These issues were similarly reported by Mehrunnissa Khanom, H.D.C. Priyadarshani and Ward-Steinman & Madura. [28,31,33] Many other researchers have discussed the same obstacles and difficulties related to online teaching and learning in their research. [15,21,25,30,34-36]

Despite its drawbacks, 57% of faculty preferred a blend of online and offline teaching, while 50% of students favored traditional in-person classes post-pandemic. The research conducted by Lyngdoh M et al at NEIGRIHMS & Joshi K et al in India, Singh et al in Nepal, Motte-Signoret E et al in France, and Wen Li et al in China showed that students did not prefer online classes for the future. [5,14,18,37,38] Conversely, studies by Kashora and Charles, Meeta Gupta, Lakbala, and Autti et al indicated strong future support for the incorporation of online education alongside traditional classroom teaching. [39-41] Students can actively engage and effectively communicate with teachers and patients in classroom and clinical settings when they are physically present, which aids in learning skills through observation and execution. Developing and refining essential skills in undergraduate medical education is crucial and requires working closely with real, volunteer, and standardized patients. This study had a few limitations. First, the sample size was small, involving only four medical colleges in Gujarat due to time constraints. Expanding the study to include more medical colleges across the state or country with a larger sample size could provide more comprehensive insights. Second, there is a potential for recall bias, as some survey questions required participants to remember their experiences during online sessions held during the Covid-19 pandemic. This reliance on memory could affect the accuracy of the data.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic and ensuing lockdowns have revolutionized medical education, pushing it from traditional face-to-face learning into the digital realm. This transition, however, was not without significant challenges. Respondents in this study highlighted key difficulties, including a lack of motivation and interest, insufficient technical knowledge, data limitations, the absence of face-to-face interaction, and a poor learning environment. While the majority acknowledged online teaching as a viable alternative during the crisis, with various benefits, over 90% of participants opposed relying solely on this method in the future.

While online classes cannot entirely replace face-to-face teaching, they can serve as a valuable complement to traditional methods with careful

planning, thorough training, and by addressing the challenges of e-learning.

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References

- United Nations. UNSDG | Policy Brief: Education during COVID-19 and beyond [Internet]. unsdg.un.org. 2020. Available from: <https://unsdg.un.org/resources/policy-brief-education-during-covid-19-and-beyond> [Last accessed on 2024 August 23]
- Burgess S, Sievertsen HH. Schools, skills, and learning: The impact of COVID-19 on education [Internet]. VoxEU. 2020. Available from: <https://voxeu.org/article/impact-covid-19-education> [Last accessed on 2024 August 23].
- Asian News International. Covid-19 Lockdown: MHA instructs educational institutes to maintain academic calendar through online teaching [Internet]. India Today. India Today; 2020 [cited 2024 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/news/story/covid-19-lockdown-mha-instructs-educational-institutes-to-maintain-academic-calendar-through-online-teaching-1667242-2020-04-15>.
- Amoah CA, Naah AM. Pre-Service Teachers' Perception of Online Teaching and Learning during the COVID – 19 Era. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*. 2020 Oct 2; 8(10):1649–62.
- Joshi K., Jamadar D., Dixit R. Joshi K, Jamadar D, Dixit R. Perception of faculty toward online teaching and learning in the undergraduate medical students during coronavirus disease-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*. 2020;9(8):484-7
- Singh V, Thurman A. How Many Ways Can We Define Online Learning? A Systematic Literature Review of Definitions of Online Learning (1988-2018). *American Journal of Distance Education*. 2019 Oct 1; 33(4):289–306.
- Howlett D, Vincent T, Gainsborough N, Fairclough J, Taylor N, and Cohen J, et al. Integration of a Case-Based Online Module into an Undergraduate Curriculum: What is involved and is it Effective? *E-Learning and Digital Media*. 2009 Jan; 6(4):372–84.
- Cook DA, Triola MM. What is the role of e-learning? Looking past the hype. *Medical Education*. 2014 Aug 11; 48(9):930–7.
- Salem AH. Randomized Controlled Trial of Simulation - Based Teaching versus Traditional Clinical Instructions in Nursing: a Pilot Study among Critical Care Nursing Students. *International Journal of Nursing Education*. 2015; 7(1):274.
- CHUMLEY-JONES HS, DOBBIE A, ALFORD CL. Web-based Learning. *Academic Medicine*. 2002 Oct; 77(Supplement):S86–93.
- Nassoura, A.B. Measuring Students' Perceptions of Online Learning in Higher Education. *Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res*. 2020; 9:1965–70.
- Mishra L, Gupta T, Shree A. Online Teaching-Learning in Higher Education during Lockdown Period of COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open* [Internet]. 2020 Sep; 1(1):100012. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666374020300121>
- Elsaid NMAB, El Nagar H, Kamal D, Bayoumi MY, Kamel MG, Abuzeid AA, et al. Perception of Online Learning among Undergraduate Students at Suez Canal Medical School during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Cross-Sectional Study. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2021 Oct 1; 85(1):2870–8.
- Singh R, Subedi M, Pant S, Rai P, Gupta K, Thapa A, et al. Perception towards Online Teaching-learning in Medical Education among Medical Students during COVID-19 Outbreak in Nepal: A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *Journal of Nepal Medical Association*. 2021 Feb 28; 59(234):128-33.
- Muthuprasad T, Aiswarya S, Aditya KS, Jha G. Students' perception and preference for online education in India during COVID -19 pandemic. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*. 2021 Jan 1; 3(1):100101.
- Rathee, Neeru & Sarkar, Chiranjit. (2020). COVID-19 Lockdown: How the Pandemic Bringing Change in Indian Education System.
- Kan D, Jing Z, Yang H, Sun W, Liu X, GAO X. Research and analysis of online learning of clinical theory course for medical undergraduates. *China Med Educ Tech*. 2020; 3:267–70.
- Li W, Gillies R, He M, Wu C, Liu S, Gong Z, et al. Barriers and facilitators to online medical and nursing education during the COVID-19 pandemic: perspectives from international students and their teaching staff. *Human Resources for Health*. 2021 May 12; 19(1).
- Al-Balas M, Al-Balas HI, Jaber HM, Obeidat K, Al-Balas H, Aborajoo EA, et al. Distance learning in clinical medical education amid COVID-19 pandemic in Jordan: current situation, challenges, and perspectives. *BMC Medical Education* [Internet]. 2020 Oct 2; 20(1). Available from: <https://bmcomeduc.biomed>

- central.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-020-02257-4
20. Peedikayil, F. C., Chandru, T.P., Kottayi, S., Purakkal, A.T., Ismail, S., John, S. Reflections and perceptions of Online Teaching and Learning in Dentistry during COVID-19. *South-East Asian Journal of Medical Education* 2020; 14(2):74-80
 21. Pande V, Menon P, Jadhav S, Agarkhedkar S. Perception of faculty and students about E-learning – its feasibility, acceptance, and implementation in COVID pandemic crisis. *Journal of Marine Medical Society*. 2021; 23:167-70.
 22. Aziz Ansari K, Farooqi FA, Qadir Khan S, Alhareky M, C Trinidad MA, Abidi T, M M. Perception on Online Teaching and Learning Among Health Sciences Students in Higher Education Institutions during the COVID-19 Lockdown - Ways to Improve Teaching and Learning in Saudi Colleges and Universities. *F1000Res*. 2021 Mar 4; 10:177. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.28178.2. PMID: 33824717; PMCID: PMC7993406.
 23. Ramachandran K, Dinesh Kumar R. Perception of medical students about online learning in the COVID-19 era. *Biomedicine*. 2021 Apr 2; 41(1):139–45.
 24. Kulal A, Nayak A. A study on perception of teachers and students toward online classes in Dakshina Kannada and Udupi District. *Asian Association of Open Universities Journal*. 2020 Oct 29; 15(3):285–96.
 25. Saha SM, Pranty SA, Rana MdJ, Islam MdJ, Hossain MdE. Teaching during a pandemic: do university teachers prefer online teaching? *Heliyon*. 2022 Jan; 8(1):e08663.
 26. Tuma F, Nassar AK, Kamel MK, Knowlton LM, Jawad NK. Students and faculty perception of distance medical education outcomes in resource-constrained system during COVID-19 pandemic. A cross-sectional study. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*. 2021 Feb; 62:377–82.
 27. Kim KJ, Kim G, Kang Y. Faculty perceptions and use of e-learning resources for medical education and future predictions: a cross sectional study. *Research Square (Research Square)*. 2022 Mar 30. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1468837/v1>.
 28. Khanom M, Hoque A, Sharif PI, Uddin ATMM, Hossain MA, Sabuj MU. Teachers' Perception on Virtual Teaching Learning Activities and Assessment: Web-based Study on a Non-Government Medical College in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Medical Education*. 2021 Mar 7; 12(1):3–9.
 29. Babita Dubey, Shivendra Singh. Perception of teachers on online teaching in higher education during Covid 19 lockdown. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts* 2020; 8(5):1017-22.
 30. Almahasees Z, Mohsen K, Amin MO. Faculty's and Students' Perceptions of Online Learning during COVID-19. *Frontiers in Education* [Internet]. 2021 May 12; 6(638470). Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2021.638470/full>
 31. Priyadarshani HDC, Jesuiya D. Teacher's Perception on Online Teaching method during Covid-19: With Reference to School Level Teachers at Faculty of Education, The Open University of Sri Lanka. *Shanlax International Journal of Education* [Internet]. 2021 Mar 1; 9(2):132–40. Available from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1287648.pdf>
 32. Chodorow S. Educators must take the electronic revolution seriously. *Academic Medicine*. 1996 Mar; 71(3):221–6.
 33. Patrice Madura Ward-Steinman. Confidence in teaching improvisation according to the K-12 achievement standards: surveys of vocal Jazz workshop participants and undergraduates. *Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education*. 2007 Jan 1; (172):25–40.
 34. Kapoor A, Kapoor A, Kailash Charokar, Mishra A, ManjunathV Motagi, SahebraoK Sada warte. Faculty survey about online teaching during early lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic in a medical college in central India. *CHRISMED Journal of Health and Research*. 2020 Jan 1; 7(4):265–5.
 35. Shalini Sobti, Gupta M, Singh M, Gupta R, Gupta P, Gupta V, et al. The perception of the medical faculty and undergraduate students regarding online teaching in the era of COVID-19. *International Journal of Academic Medicine*. 2021 Jan 1; 7(3):156–6.
 36. Bączek M, Zagańczyk-Bączek M, Szpringer M, Jaroszyński A, Woźakowska-Kapłon B. Students' perception of online learning during the COVID-19. *Medicine. LWW* [Internet]. 2021 Feb 19; 100(7). Available from: https://journals.lww.com/md-journal/Fulltext/2021/02190/Students_perception_of_online_learning_during_the.87.aspx.
 37. Lyngdoh M, Devi NJ, Medhi GK. Perception of online teaching in medical education in the backdrop of COVID- -19 lockdown: a cross – sectional study among medical students of NE-IGRIHMS. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2021 Nov 24; 8(12):5913.
 38. Motte-Signoret E, Labbé A, Benoist G, Linglart A, Gajdos V, Lapillonne A. Perception of medical education by learners and teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic: a cross-sectional survey of online teaching. *Medical Education Online*. 2021 Jan 1; 26(1):1919042.

39. Kashora FK, Charles DA. Online-learning: exploring practices among Foundation doctors. *J Adv Med Educ Prof.* 2019 Jan; 7(1):14-19.
40. Lakbala P. Barriers in Implementing E-Learning in Hormozgan University of Medical Sciences. *Global Journal of Health Science.* 2015 Nov 3; 8(7):83-92.
41. Autti T, Autti H, Vehmas T, Laitalainen V, Kivisaari L. E-learning is a well-accepted tool in supplementary training among medical doctors: an experience of obligatory radiation protection training in healthcare. *Acta Radiologica.* 2007 Jun; 48(5):508–13.